
IMPERATIVE OF VALUE RE-ORIENTATION IN BOKO-HARAM INSURGENCE AND TERRORISTS, POST-CONFLICT SOCIETIES (A CASE OF YOBE STATE, NIGERIA).

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ABSTRACT

For any nation or country to develop meaningfully, her citizens must cultivate good values, in recent times, there has been general outcry over decaying value standards in Nigeria. Selfish and undesirable values have replaced wholesome ones thereby leading to unhealthy developments. This clearly demonstrates that all is not well with our nation (Nigeria) where the values we once held dearly, have been thrown into the trash bin. The erosion of societal values which manifests in varied unpatriotic and antisocial behaviour of most Nigerian has been a disturbing issue to all and sundry. This social problem requires formal and institutional strategies to address. Efforts by previous Nigerian governments are known to have achieved little, the major bowl of contention is the super-imposition of alien values, perspective, beliefs and superstition on our society to the neglect of indigenous ones, our worries over value disorientation indicate that both the individual and society have shifted from the cohesiveness of traditional values to the confusion and uncertainty of modernity This paper therefore, takes a cursory look at the concepts of values, value reorientation, the imperative of value reorientation in Boko- Haram insurgency post conflict society in Yobe State Nigeria where there had been incidence of terrorists attacks, destruction of life and property displacement of thousands of people from their place of abode and forceful conscription of people into militant camps. This research maintains that the Family, Government, Educational Institutions, Religious Organizations and the Media remain the fulcrum of value reorientation in Nigerian and must continue to play their roles as value educators because there can be no positive developments in a country with misplaced values.

Keywords: Imperative, Value, re-orientation, Boko-Haram, Post-Conflict, Society.

Introduction and background to the study:

North-Eastern Nigeria, particularly Yobe State has suffered some setbacks as a result of anti-social and criminal acts, insurgence and terrorism, with high rate of violence, The decline and fall in moral behavior has reached unacceptable level as the region has become home of terrorist and kidnapers where human life has become nothing and properties destroy day in day out, with thousands of people displaced and homeless. There is therefore, no other words to describe this scenario than decadence of value both for human life and societal norms. Value shares the same meaning with morality as it depicts the acceptable conduct of behaviour in the society. Values are standards that guide and determine actions, attitudes towards objects and situations. Values are things that are socially or culturally acquired, perception of what is desirable or not, which ultimately influences their choice and behaviour. Consequently, value implies acceptable standards, ideal way of doing things and living virtuous life in society. Values can be seen as the guiding principles that order the life of individuals. They help to shape attitudes and beliefs and create differences in the way significant issues are seen.

Similarly, value re-orientation is view as means, methods, ways of restoring or making changes of attitude towards a number of things that have been identified as wrong action or wrong attitude in a given society or organization. Value reorientation can be viewed as re-directing the attention of the citizens on the acceptance of social, economic, cultural, intellectual, political, moral and aesthetic norms of the society. It is the genuine and consistent efforts made by individuals, families, societies, communities, nations or organizations to revive or restore back the bastardized values for which they were known in order to re-sharpen the life styles of their members as well as moving the society forward. Value re-orientation is a process of changing the old and inappropriate value orientation of an individual to enable him acquires new set of values that are more appropriate for good citizenship, nation building and political stability (Isiakpere, 2005).

In Nigeria, there is a great need for value re-orientation of the society and the youth in particular in order to ensure that every citizen respects the societal norms and values as well as the nation's constitution, adoption of democratic principles in leadership and fair sharing of political/ social powers. It will ensure that citizens are loyal and obedient to the government and the rule of law in addition to the love of the nation first before personal gains and thereby contributing to the development of the Nigerian nation

Through the centuries, one of the most important problems confronting philosophers and educators, is the problem of values, generally known as aetiology. Values influence people's behaviour and serve as a yardstick for evaluating the actions of other people in the society. In the domain of education, values are paramount, for they are tightly bound to the general idea of education and the operation of schools. Education must be something worthwhile and being worthwhile has value implication. Thus, values are standards, reputations, right attitudes, worth, rules and regulations for the way people should do things and cut across moral conducts, dressing codes, socialization and greeting, walking steps, sitting positions, table manners and so on. Man is a creature of choice; he is a free moral agent. Everyone has the choice to live right or wrong.

For any society to experience positive and sustainable growth, positive values must be upheld and encouraged. Where social values have decayed, underdevelopment sets in hence the need for reorientation of values. NEEDS (2004) described Nigeria as a multi-ethnic society, with a value system that is derived from the diversity of its people, religion and culture. These core

values NEEDS identified include respect for elders, honesty and accountability, co-operation, industry, discipline, self-confidence and moral courage.

According to Okoh (2003), value connotes something important that is qualitatively cherished: something that provides satisfaction or sense of accomplishment". Okpilike (2010) views values as one's principles or standards, and judgments of what is valuable and important to life. According to Hill (2004), values are the priorities individuals and societies attach to certain beliefs, experiences and objects, in deciding how they shall live and what they shall treasure. Enu and Esu (2011) note that values are basic beliefs and attitude in a society whether of individuals or groups which are considered worthwhile and serve as a guide to choices and behaviors in our daily life. Value thus implies acceptable standards, ideal way of doing things and living virtuous life in society. Values therefore are deep seated beliefs that influence people's actions and behaviors. Okoh (2003) identifies various types of values to include the following: Religious Moral, Aesthetic, Social, Cultural, Intellectual and Economic.

Statement of research Problem

With all sense of honesty and sincerity, all is not well with our nation (Nigeria) mainly because of our misplacement of values. The need for attitudinal re-orientation had long been recognized as the best way to address our myriads of societal problems confronting the Nigerian society. Consequently, successive administrations have articulated and pursued re-orientation programs in one form or the other, regrettable, however, despite all the attempts, programs and interventions, nothing can be seen in concrete terms as reward and achievements to the enormous work of re-branding Nigeria. There still exist all the negative attributes that hold us down as a nation. The concern of this study is, however, on moral values. Moral values are honesty, liberty, justice, brotherhood, neighborliness, among other morals. It is a matter of conscience. It is the conscience that makes an individual consider the effects of what he is planning to do on the other people. These values guide man's conducts towards his fellow man. A closer look at the above description, would make one agree that Nigeria would be rapidly transformed if she embraces good moral values, which have the potentials to re-orientate the attitude and behaviors of Nigerians and to bring significant reduction in corruption, indiscipline, immorality, terrorism, kidnapping ..What are the positive attitudes and values that will ensure citizens discipline and development in Nigeria?

Literature review

The Nigerian Value System

Generally, Nigerian values are embedded in the people's social, economic and political institutions. These institutions spell out moral principles which members of the society should be acquainted with and must pass on to the younger generations. In this institutional framework, the family constitutes one of the basic fulcrums of the survival of the people and society. Although it is the smallest unit of human social organization, its significance in the survival of people and their cultures is fundamental. It is the beginning of the process of socialization and impacts the basic ethical and moral principles in the child. The family sets the basic moral guidelines, what should be done, and what not to do and why certain forms of behaviours are to be preferred; why there should be acceptable character, enviable conduct and good conscience.

The child as a member of the society, learns to believe and accept the sanctity of life, obedience to constituted authority, believe in the ontological harmony which is superintended

over by the supreme being; acceptance of one's state of life, and so on. Thus, the value system encompasses a ray of moral principles passed on to the younger ones through traditional and indigenous education system which emphasizes that one is first a member of the community being an individual and whatever affects him affects the rest of the community. If he commits crime, the community is brought into disrepute, but if he excels, the community rejoices. Evidently, the advent of colonialism with its attendant capitalist structures brought imported ethical values to our society which is alien to us. These new ethical values are based on the capitalist system of production which emphasize individualism and self-contentedness.

These decay values act as impediments to a smooth and desirable economic development since everybody is concerned with achieving this selfish interest not minding whether others survive or not. Thus, individual consciousness becomes the source of moral judgement. What is good or bad, right or wrong is no longer what the community approves but what the individual feels and decides for himself. Nnadozie (2010) citing Ukoha (1992) observed that although there is diversity in Nigerian culture, there are common values, which cut across cultures. These values include hard-work, honesty, humility, diligence, love towards fellow men, industry, maintenance of standard of living within one's income, respect for elders among others.

Value reorientation in Nigeria

The core of every human culture or ethos of any culture is a mark of its fundamental values. The satisfaction of some desires and interests informs the values we placed on things or experiences that arise from them. The objectivity of value is a personal judgment with pronounced emotional tone (Njoku, 2006). The issue of value reorientation and the call for it is long overdue, this is because concerned stakeholders have expressed shock over the rate of deteriorating values in the polity as expressed in attitude and disposition of youths. This justifies the need for value reorientation in the society. By value reorientation we simply mean that, those cherished values of the society which makes societies developed should be re-invented and re-instilled into the citizens so as to turn the negative values they have acquired for themselves over the years via different platform, exposure and experiences into positive. It then explains why there is a dire need for citizens to undergo value reorientation in Nigeria if truly we wish to build a better nation with pride in the true sense of the world. Value reorientation entails re-educating the citizens on values and enlightening them on what values entails as well as making them aware of the values they should possess at any point in time which are considered essential to their personal growth and development as well as building of the nation as a whole.

The above question is indeed a million-dollar question which has been hanging in the minds of many over the years. It is crystal clear that our people today are perpetrators of immoral acts which gives rise to worries as to whether the educational institution is really inculcating values into the citizen or not and if the school is dully exercising her responsibility what then could be the cause and rise in immoral acts among Nigerian citizens. While stressing the need for early inculcation of patriotic ideals and values in pupils, Abah (2014) was of the opinion that early exposure of citizens to values would elicit in them a local and national consciousness of societal values and respect for public property.

This will help to ensure rounded growth and develop national consciousness in them which will foster their individual as well as collective effort towards nation building. Youths can constitute nuisance or threat to nation building and stability if they are misguided, unemployed, indisciplined, and allowed to drift away and be morally bankrupt (Egbunefu, 2014). In his own view, Olaopa (2016) disclosed that the whole nation needs widespread

reorientation on national values as basis for re-engineering of fundamental governance institutions to infuse public institutions with cultural and spirituality service.

This shows that, values re-orientation is key to nation building as the case may be. Olaopa (2016) added that National Orientation Agency (NOA) should be elevated to create values, attitude guidelines, and practical initiatives that could be integrated into development policies, planning and programs. In an attempt to ensure value reorientation for Nigerian citizens, the Federal government introduced National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS). NEEDS which was launched on 29th, May 2004 by Nigeria government had value reorientation as one of its four major goals (National Planning Commission (NPC, 2004). The portion reads 'NEEDS will lay a solid foundation for sustainable poverty reduction, employment generation, wealth creation and value reorientation'. The Change Catalyst (2013) opined that 'NEEDS is anchored on the imperative to restore the fundamental values of Nigeria, which have been weakened over the years.

From the discussions above, it seems clear that values are basic beliefs and attitude in a society whether of individual or groups which are considered worthwhile and which serve as guide to choices and behavior in daily life. Values therefore, are things or ideas we hold in high esteem or regard highly. So, value re-orientation is the process of changing an individual's, group of individuals' or society's poor value of a concept to a positive one.

Aim and Objective of the Research Work

The cardinal aim of this research is a renewal and call for ethical and value reorientation among the people of North-Eastern Nigeria, Yobe State in particular and the nation at large.

1. To examine the reasons for the falling standard of our ethical values and principles
2. To identify factors responsible for the falling standard in our ethical values and principles
3. To see what can be done in order to revive our ethical values and principles

Research Questions

1. What are the reasons for the erosion and deterioration of our ethical values and principles?
2. What are the factors responsible for the decaying and deteriorating nature of our values and principles?
3. What strategies can be adopted for value re-orientation among the people in the North-Eastern Nigeria and Nigeria at large?

Research location:

This research is essentially on the imperative of value reorientation in the Boko Haram insurgency; terrorist affected communities. The study area is Yobe state, North Eastern part of Nigeria created in 1991 from Borno state. Geographically, the state is located at latitude 110N and Longitude 13.50E and spans through 47, 153 km² of land and shares boundary with the Republic of Benin (Bello, 2013a). To the South West of Yobe state is bounded by Bauchi and Gombe states. The state also shares common boundaries with Borno state to the East and South East and Jigawa state in the North West. According to the National Population Commission (NPC) 2006 census the population of the state is 2, 321,591 people, it one of the states with the lowest population density of 49 people per km² in Nigeria (Eze and Olabimtan, 2010). There are seventeen Local Government Areas (LGAs) in the state and they include Bade, Busari, Damaturu, Fika, Fune, Geidam, Gujba, Gulani, Jakusko, Karasuwa, Machina, Nangere, Nguru, Potiskum, Tarmuwa, Yunusari and Yusufari (Terver et al.,

2014). Yobe state is one of the states where Boko-Haram insurgents and terrorists has unleashed untold hardship on the people and destroyed properties worth billions of naira since the year 2009 up to-date.

Yobe State Population by Local Government Areas

(2006 Nigeria Population Census).

S/N	Local Govt. Area	Population
1	Bade	139804
2	Bursari	109,692
3	Damaturu	87,706
4	Fika	136,736
5	Fune	301,954
6	Geidam	155,740
7	Gujba	129,797
8	Gulani	103,516
9	Jakusko	232,458
10	Karasuwa	105,514
11	Machina	60,994
12	Nangere	87,517
13	Nguru	150,699
14	Potiskum	204,866
15	Tarmuwa	77,667
16	Yunusari	125,940
17	Yusufari	110,739
	Total	2,321.339

Gender; Male = 1,205.034 (51.91%), Female = 1,116305 (48.09%)

(Source: 2006. Nigeria National Population Commission)

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Research Approach

This research work employs Questionnaire (structured) and interview to gain a better knowledge of the situation and issues affecting the post-conflict society and the need for reorientation in the study area, as well as, their view of the possible ways of inculcating the right attitudes and values among the people. The target population in this study is the population of Yobe state which, according to the National Population Commission 2006 census report is, 2,321.33 made up of seventeen local government areas and of which a sample size of 150 respondents will be randomly taken as sample size through survey (administration of questionnaire) using Cochran sample size determination formula. However, this will form the bases of analysis. The content and design of the questionnaire will be critically re-evaluated to ensure effectiveness in its use for gathering the necessary data. By so doing, it will ease the rigor of handling data for data processing and analysis. The questionnaire is administered randomly.

The erosion of societal values which manifests in varied unpatriotic and anti-social behavior of most of the people has been a disturbing issue to all and sundry. This is a social problem that requires formal and institutional strategies to address. Efforts by previous Nigerian governments are known to have hit the rocks. The major area of attack on our development is the super-imposition of alien values, perspective, beliefs, superstition and idiosyncrasies on our society to the neglect of indigenous ones. According to Nnachi (2003), our worries over value disorientation indicate that both the individual and society have shifted from the cohesiveness of traditional values to the confusion and uncertainty of modernity. This change has been attributed to technological and economic factors. We are all aware that our efforts toward scientific and technological development can hardly yield the desired results unless there is a conducive social/psychological development within the society, hence Nigerians need re-orientation on the highly esteemed societal values. Value re-orientation is necessary because as Onyeachu (2008) observed, it is the society values that determines the tone and level of development of that society. The greatest worry about our value system is that some of the values pursued by many Nigerians, especially the leaders, do not promote national unity and development. Therefore, there is urgent need for a new value order or a better value orientation at all levels. The crisis of values in Nigeria suggests that the growth and progress of the society is being retarded in many aspects through outburst of materialistic tendencies of the citizens. It is beyond doubt that materialism has taken over government, political institutions, invaded traditional and cultural institutions, while the church seems to be more materialistic than the secular society. The malady of value crisis has predicated Nigeria as open society in which anything goes. In Nigeria we seem to be grabbing the worst and getting very little of the best from the rest of the world. This paper on value reorientation of people in post-conflict societies is focused on redeeming the people currently faced with crushing identity crisis, resulting from misplacement and abuse of values. No doubt, Nigeria had national culture that established her, before materialistic invasion and the family remains the primary base for value formation and reorientation. Government at all levels, educational institutions and religious organizations must all play significant roles in our quest for value reorientation of Nigerian in order to attract national development

The method used in the collection of data is survey method which involves the use of structured questionnaire and interview aimed at eliciting necessary information and data from respondents in the affected areas on the imperative of re-orientating the citizens about societal norms and value which binds the people. The population of the study area Yobe state is 2,532,989 according to Nigeria 2006 national population census, it is made up of seventeen (17) local government areas and has three senatorial districts, zones A, B and C. It is one of the states in the North-eastern part of Nigeria with a male population of 1,801,324 and a female population of 1,723,164, (2006 population census). A sample size of one hundred and fifty (150) respondents is taken, fifty (50) from each senatorial districts (50 x 3) to whom questionnaire will be administered to elicit relevant data an information to address the necessity and imperative of re-orientating citizens in post conflict societies 142 people answered and returned the questionnaires which is 95% of the sample size which is adequate for analysis on the subject matter (the imperative of value re-orientation in post conflict societies), twenty (20) questions are raised apart from the bio-data information of the respondents which sought to know the gender, age, occupation, qualification and experience as well as marital status of respondents as a prelude to understanding their status in society and their knowledge.

Eighty seven (87) respondents of the sampled population which 142 people are male and they constitute 61% while 55 respondents which is 39% of the sampled population are female, the occupation of respondents shows that 64 respondents are practicing farmer (herdsmen and cultivating farmers) they constitute 45% of the sampled population, 48 respondents which is 34% are civil servants 27 respondents are unemployed youths which is 19% of sample population this is a pointer to the issue of or problem in inquiry, if 19% of 142 respondents which is 27 respondents are unemployed youth certainly there is bound to be violence, disregard for constituted authority and disregard for norms and values as witnessed in the North-Eastern Nigeria (Yobe in particular), 3 respondents 2.1% are contractors engaged in petty construction, maintenance/repairs and supply works.

The ages of the respondent runs from 18-30 which are 23 people representing 16%, ages 31-40 are 38 people which is 27% of sample population and ages 41-50 are 47 people representing 33% of sampled population while 61-60 are 20 people representing 14% of the sampled population and ages 61 and above are 14 respondents which is 9.8% of the sampled population. This implies that the age range of 18-40 when added makeup 61 respondents representing 43% of sampled population are youths which are considered to be the active labour force of a nation, who ought to be engaged and deployed in the labour force for production of goods and services and for manufacturing, mining and providing other social services for the population, unfortunately a greater percentage of this group are unemployed with little or low level of education (high level of unemployment and illiteracy) this further buttress the tendency for high level of violence, terrorism and insurgency in the study area, 27 respondents have no western education they constitute 19% sample population, Those with primary school level education are 43 respondent constitute 29% of sampled size, 59 respondents which 39.9% are secondary school certificate holders while 19 respondents which is 13.3% of the sampled population are holders of higher degrees (ND, HND, BSc, MSc and PhD) respectively.

From the bio-data of the respondents of the sampled population it can be inferred that there is high level of unemployment among the youth ages (18-40) and also low level of education within the same age range. This no doubt points to factors responsible for neglects and abuse of norms, disrespect for societal values and consequently violence and terrorism among others. The research findings on issues of people awareness and recognition of the decay of societal norms, and values as well as the imperative and necessity for re-orientation and restoring the values and cultures.

One hundred and forty-two (142) questionnaires were distributed across the three senatorial districts which is 95%. Twenty questions were raised to elicit information and data on the issue of decay of value, norms and the need for re-orientation of citizens. Firstly it was ascertained that every human society has its own norms, values and laws which guides its existence survival and the conduct of its citizen. 126 respondents represent 89% of the sampled population which is 142 people strongly agree that every human society has norms, values and laws which regulate the conduct of her citizen. While the remaining 16 respondents representing 11% agree to the existence of norms, values and laws in all human society, there is however no disagree or strongly disagree on the issue, importantly there is no society without its own norms, values and law which guide the conduct of the of its citizens. In the same vein 119 respondents representing 83% of the sampled population opined that societies where norms and values are upheld and respected. it enhances peaceful co-existence and harmony 23 respondent which is 16% of sampled population also agree to this. Majority of respondents about 136 people which is 96% sampled population say negligence or neglect of social norms and values create disorder and lawlessness in society, this position is also

supported by 6 respondents which is 4% of sampled population, non disagree or strongly disagree with this position. It is also the belief of 127 respondent which is 89% of sampled population that societies where there are stipulated punishment for breaking societal norms and laws people adhere to them in order to avoid punishment or been punished, 12 respondents which is 8% of the sampled population also toll the line of majority while 3 respondents which is 2.1% disagree with this position, they however consist insignificant number of the sampled population.

A reasonable number of respondents of about 132 people represent 93% of sampled population opined that norms and values are not permanent or static in any society, as society evolve or changesthe norms and values of society also changes in conformity with prevailing circumstances or needs in this respect laws are made to address issues (problem) as new issues emerges new laws are made to cater for the emerging issues. 6 respondents which is 4% of the sampled population disagree and opined that norm and values ought to be permanent and static, so as to make it known to everybody, they buttress their view with norms and values in traditional societies which are often held in high esteem because it is sacrosanct and permanent in nature.

Research findings reveal that western culture and ways of life has seriously influenced and affected our societies and our conducts through, western education. Videos, films, television, radio and other social media, we consciously or unconsciously copy and imitate western values, mode of dressing, disregard for elders, nonchalant attitude among others. 134 respondents which constitute 94% of the sampled population affirmed this position that western civilization and influence has eaten deeply into our societal values and culture, thereby undermining our cherished norms and values while others disagree that western civilization influence has little or nothing to do with our norms and values.

It can however be argued that foreign movies, films, videos, pornography and social media has hard significant influence on our youths and societies, issues such as homosexuality, gay marriage, lesbianism, cocaine, marijuana, heroin among other addictions has changed the lifestyle of our youths negatively and they conversely indulge in violent activities criminality, terrorism and disregard for societal norms and values, this buttress the fact that violence and terrorism are alien to our culture and tradition, particularly in Northern region of Nigeria, this view is supported by 128 respondent 90% of the sampled population while the remaining 14 respondents which represent 10% of the sampled size opined or argued that decay of norms and values cannot be completely attributed to westernization or civilization alone even though they contribute in some greater measure, notwithstanding there are domestic and internal factors within the society which often lead to neglect of norms and values and as well leading to violent conflicts, they argued that issues such as poverty, unemployment, religious radicalism, marginalization, poor economic situation, hunger, lack of basic needs of life such as food shelter, clothing, water, lack of health-care facilities, poor infrastructure, denial of rights/ benefits and opportunities, class antagonism , and class rivalry among others are internal factors responsible for neglect and abuse of norms, laws, values and laid down procedures of carrying out things or achieving goals. Therefore people violate laws and norms not because they deliberately want to break rules but because circumstances and need to achieve their goals which they cannot achieve through the conventional laid down procedures, they therefore boycott conventional means and ways by going through unconventional ways and means to achieve their goals and objectives, hence violence, rigging, disregard for rules and procedure, intimidation, forceful taking over of people's property, killings and destruction of property among others.

This is why most people believe that Boko-Haram insurgency and terrorist activities in North-eastern Nigeria and particularly in Yobe state, where the sect originated can be attributed to the decay of norms and values, this argument holds water when collaborated with the views expressed above by majority of the respondents of the sampled population, it is important to say that whichever factors may be responsible for decay of our norms and values, either western civilization such as videos-films, pornographic-films, modernity, cultural infiltration, western media, social media or globalization or domestic internal factors such as poverty, unemployment, marginalization, hunger, class rivalry among others, what is of importance and necessity is re-orientation of the citizens to the hitherto cherished and functional norms and values which holds and binds society together in unity and progress, there has to be concerted efforts by all and sundry, governments, groups individuals, families, associations and organizations need to put in place programs, enlightenment, mobilizations, awareness about the decays and negligence of our norms and values and the urgent need to resuscitate, revive and resonate them for a better and more humane society where peace, harmony and tranquility can reign again as it were in the earlier days of our society. Apportioning blames and excuses on groups of people, governments and individual is not the solution to the issue but rather to see that there is urgent need to re-orient citizens in post-conflicts, especially in war-torn societies in North-eastern Nigeria and indeed Yobe state, because of the significant and importance of the state as the origin of the Boko-Haram sect and their activities that has refused to end.

Government must embark on aggressive public enlightenment and education through mass media, social media, National Orientation Agency and other avenue and ways to inculcate values, respect and law abiding in the citizen. Traditional institutions and rulers have very important roles to play in social re-orientation towards positive values. Religious bodies and organizations could also serve and be used in inculcating the right values in the citizens (if properly used). Educational institutions at all levels (primary, secondary and tertiary) must be made to key in properly in the teaching and inculcating the right values and norms in to the citizens, (Educational or School Curriculum) must have norms and values re-orientation as one of their cardinal subjects. Similarly, the educational system must be accorded more importance through proper funding, infrastructural provision, teaching facilities, quality and competent teachers, so as to make it viable for teaching and learning and inculcating the right values into the citizens.

Importantly the family which is the smallest unit of the society and the bedrock of socialization and child upbringing, the first institution of contact for children in terms of morality, values, norms and attitudinal building and changes must wake up to its traditional responsibility and role in the society so as to inculcate the necessary right values into the children from inception or beginning of life.

It has been argued by majority of the respondents from the sampled population of 142 people that decadence of our societal norms, values and etiquette is attributed to breakdown of family system characterized by divorce broken homes, wayward children, street girls, single mothers, lesbianism among others. The family must be brought to play her role in child upbringing and socialization as against the present situation of single parents, broken homes, scattered families, Area boys, yahoo boys, single father, spinster and the likes. Government must discourage gay marriages, single parents' lesbianism, street girls, Area boys and must also revive children's home, amusement parks, social networking, remand homes and proper children care and child care centers.

Government must pay attention to its internal security, maintenance of law and order, protection of lives and properties which are one of the cardinal duties of government all over

the world must be given its deserved priority through strengthening the military, police force, civil defense corps and other paramilitary agencies charged with the responsibility of maintaining law and order. Regular training of members of the armed forces, modern equipment and communication gadgets and proper remuneration of staff will enhance coordinated effort towards maintaining law and order and conversely peace and stability. Most importantly basic needs of life, food, water, shelter, health-care services, provision of employment opportunity, reduction in the level of poverty reduction in the level of illiteracy through proper education and diminishing the level of ignorance will no doubt bring about respect and adhere to norms, laws and a peaceful society.

Conclusion: orientation and re-orientation is an age long discourse in Nigeria which has led government to introduce some institutions, agencies, programs and policies in the bid to inculcating the right values in the citizens. In the late 1980 and early 1990, the Mass Mobilization for Social Justice and Self-Reliance (MAMSER) took the lead in social orientation and mobilization of the citizens, the organization engaged in different programs and efforts aimed at inculcating the right values and attitudinal changes in the citizens at all levels and could be adjudged as having made remarkable changes, respect for constituted authority, adherence to societal norms and values as it were, the organization's name was later changed to National Orientation Agency (NOA) which can be said to be moribund as its hardly heard or seen in discharging its functions and responsibilities of social engineering and mobilization.

In the same vein, the Buhari-Idiagbon led government introduced the War Against Indiscipline and corruption (WAIC). An agency that strives to instill discipline, orderliness and limit corrupt practices in public service and in government agencies and institutions, this also to a large extent can be said to have achieved its goals and objectives, Babangida's administration however returned the country to high level of corrupt practices, settlement and embezzlement of public funds. Subsequent governments have not done anything remarkably different from Babangida's administration except some cosmetic policies and programs such as Zero Tolerance for corruption, Anti-draft policies, Whistle-Blowing policies and anti-corruption crusade of the different regimes Obasanjo, Jonathan, Buhari and of recent Tinubu's government.

Other government Agencies established to fight corruption and indiscipline includes Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), Corrupt Practices Commission (CPC) and Money Laundering Act among others all aimed at instilling discipline, moral values, and uprightness in the citizenry. Whichever way we view the role of government and her institutions in instilling discipline, values and morality, more needed to be done if we must salvage our declining values, restore our ethical norms and have a peaceful and prosperous society.

Recommendations:

- 1) It has been established that the falling standard of our ethical values and neglect of norms is responsible for the criminal activities in conflict society(ies) government must take urgent step to re-orient people in post-conflict societies through public enlightenment, education, mass media, radio and television programs and other social orientation agencies such as NOA, Art and culture among others.
- 2) Government must as a matter of importance and necessity make the teaching and learning of societal norms, values, and culture (citizenship education) compulsory at all level of education.
- 3) The family system need to be revitalized and made to play her role of child bearing, rearing and upbringing because it is the first point of contact of the child and the beginning

of moral and ethical teaching and learning to foster a unified viable and strong society, policies to enhance family growth and development need to be pursued and to stop the abuse of sexual related issues such as lesbianism, homosexuality, gay marriage, and as well as to limit or reduce divorces, single parent, adultery, fornication, street girls, child trafficking among others.

- 4) Orientation agencies must be revitalized and made more functional such as National Orientation Agency (NOA) social works, remind homes, child care, amusement parks, play centers, youth clubs, children development training and workshop must be given priority.
- 5) More attention needs to be given to internal and external security measures through the provision of adequate funding for security personnel, training, improved condition of service, remunerations (salaries and wages) to boost their morale and make them more dedicated to duty.
- 6) Also, basic needs such as water, electricity, food, shelter need to be provided and guaranteed for citizens; this will reduce conflict, if there is reduction in poverty level, hunger and unemployment, illiteracy and ignorance.
- 7) Traditional institutions and leaders must take active role in the re-orientation process of the people through inculcating the right values in the citizens.

Finally, security of lives and properties is a fundamental responsibility of all government anywhere and everywhere in the world, Nigeria's government must take the issue of her citizens' security with absolute sense of seriousness so as to have the desired peace, harmony and developments desiring of a country like ours.

Contribution to Knowledge

One of the challenges facing Nigeria is deteriorating value at the federal, state and local levels. It is critical that institutions are strengthened and the governance architecture put in place. Another critical problem is security challenges, unemployment, poverty and deteriorating health-care facilities if at all they exist, Therefore, the contribution of this research work is essentially to bring to focus the conditions of post-conflict societies or otherwise referred to as insurgence affected communities, the imperative of value re-orientation and ethical rejuvenation in post-conflict society.

Possible outcome of research

Value reorientation is not as easy as it sounds this is because the hardest thing there is to do is changing human belief and working on their psychic as it concerns affective domain. This means that it has to be deliberate, well planned, and conscious if we really intend to successfully conduct value reorientation of our people as it were. Every human society has specific characteristics of its people that distinguish the inhabitants from other society. The Nigeria value system is the beliefs, standards, principles about the right and wrong in the society. Value dictates the choices man make and choice in turn influences the behavior of every man in the society. The value system of any human society determined the level of development. Like most aspects of culture, the value system is non-material. Compared to culture and norm, it varies according to society over time. The core value of the Nigeria society is discipline, honesty, hard-work, accountability, loyalty, respect for the elderly, truthfulness etc. The national values transcend ethnic or religious faith and are concept that embody who we are as a nation. It is the value system that shapes the perception and beliefs of the people. Our values impact on every aspect of our life; religion, relationships, career, and character. They determine what we think, say or how we act. It is therefore imperative to draw the flashlight on the re-orientation of the value system of the Nigerian society vis-à-vis the decadence in the society

Dissemination of Results:

The result of this research work will be disseminated through several ways but noted able, through publication of the research outcome in reputable journals, periodicals and making copies available to the government at all levels Federal, State and Local government and more importantly to agencies and organizations working in the areas of value reorientation, peace building and ethical revolution in the affected areas, copies will also be made available in libraries around the area of concern.

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